

A Study of the Impact of Positive and Negative Emotions at Work Place

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Abstract:- In this materialistic world emotions have great importance. Today emotions have become an integral part of study of psychology. After all what is an emotion? An emotion is a state in the field of study of psychology state which involves various components such as a subjective experience, a physiological response, and response pertaining to behavior." The word emotion includes a behaviors that can be easily observed, feelings that can be easily expressed, and occurring bodily changes. Emotion is a feeling that is personal, relative and subjective. Emotions are simply energy in motion. When you experience a state of emotion it is because that energy has been triggered by some psychological feeling or thought in your mind and it got motion, which creates feelings which are experienced in various parts in your body. Emotions can travel. Generally speaking, there are two types of emotions – positive and negative. Those that are positive such as feelings of love, and happiness make you feel good and those that are negative such as feelings of anger, and disappointment make you feel terrible.

Emotions at workplace are of vital importance and help to determine how an entire organization communicates within itself and to the outside world. "Incidents which take place at work have real emotional impact on people working there. The costs of emotional states in the workplace, both in terms of behavior and attitude, have considerable implication for individuals, groups, and society. Positive emotions in the workplace result in employees obtaining favorable outcomes including achievement, job enrichment and higher quality social context. Negative emotions, such as fear, anger, stress, hostility, sadness, and guilt, however increase the probability of workplace deviance and its impact on the the outside world.

Keywords:- Emotions, workplace, physiological response, behavioral.

I. INTRODUCTION

Emotions at workplace are of vital importance and help to determine how an entire organization communicates within itself and to the outside world. "Incidents which take place at work have real emotional impact on people working there. The costs of emotional states in the workplace, both in terms of behavior and attitude, have considerable implication for individuals, groups, and society.

"Emotions normally are associated with specific actions or incidences and are strong enough to upset thought

processes. Moods on the other hand, are more "generalized feelings or states that are not typically identified with a particular stimulus and not sufficiently intense to interrupt ongoing thought processes". We cannot find a human being in the universe who is emotionless. In a span of 24 hours we come across many emotions which govern our day. Emotions are part of being human and, as a result, part of how we work. In small businesses, though, where expectations often run high and resources low, emotional outbursts can seem like the norm rather than the exception the demands of running a small business -- constant time crunch for strategic planning, the anxiety of making payroll, etc., can often be overwhelming. As a manager, there's also added pressure to maintain a management style that keeps a lid on emotions.

A. Objective of the study

- To study the various types of emotions at workplace.
- To study how positive emotions lay its footprints on the work place.
- To study how negative emotions, create work place issues and disturb the whole organization
- To study the measures to overcome of negative emotions.
- To study the role of positive emotions to productivity enhancement.

B. Scope and limitation

Emotions play a vital role in the life of a person. It affects the life of an individual to a greater extent. The scope of the study expands to all the organizations and thus occupies a prime position.

C. Limitation

The study is purely based on secondary data and hence lacks the benefits of primary data. The time period is also limited and the study is limited to general survey.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research work is done by purely using secondary data. The data is gathered from the various sources such as books, websites, management journals, ect.

We always carry our emotions at workplace. When we are overburdened with work, we get frustrated as we already are working too much and are of the feeling that our boss is emotionless and he fail to deliberately understand how much work we already have. We get upset with co-workers who are unproductive and are work avoiders and we do their work too. We get angry with enraged customers who don't

realize we are there to help them. We worry about our future which is most uncertain.

When we are struggling with these emotions, we fail to understand how to deal with it and we believe that our emotions are a result of an external cause, i.e., the situations arising in our lives or the behavior of others. It is because that's the manner how we have been taught to think about emotions. It just isn't factual.

The main objective here is not to ever have any negative emotions thought. That's not possible at all. The goal is to identify them faster and change through them quicker. That sounds something realistic. But how this can be achieved?

The first logical step towards this goal is , diagnose you've to something to do with it. Here one should not forget that emotion are Energy in MOTION that is an energy that moves continuously. At this juncture one can realise that energy is moving through your body. The root word is "emote", which implies what you are feeling. Emotions are an attempt to express externally, to express what we believe.

If your belief is insensible then you act on automatic pilot. If sensible, then you have some choice to choose from within. In any case, how you feel echoes how you think. Your negative thoughts produce negative emotions. Your positive thoughts produce positive emotions.

So, emotion is not something that happens to you. Emotion is actually something you are responsible for. If you experience an emotion then you should do something with it. Be curious about thoughts that lead emotion.

Second, understand that there are laws for emotions too. As secretive as it seems, every emotion you exhibit is a result of some thought that heralded your emotion. The only exception to this rule is if you have some chemical or neurological damage that throws everything out of slap. But if you have a healthy body then how you think causes how you feel. How you feel affects your behavior. And, how you behave gives some or the other king of results. It's just a law.

Third, accept that any choice to make changes in how you feel will always come after the circumstance. That's because we can't control your primary reaction to anything! Your habits are too influential. But you can control your second thought and in that is your saving grace.

Fig. 1: Relationship of emotions with thoughts and behavior

The 10 Common Positive Emotions are:

- Love
- Calmness
- Mercy
- Respect
- Joy
- Interest
- Hope
- Pride
- Amusement
- Inspiration

Now let us talk about how positive emotions contribute towards workplace wellness.

A hurdle free mind is the key to organizational and individual success. Our cognitive capabilities need to be in the best form to meet the daily challenges at work. Values, beliefs, positive thoughts are a prerequisite that will help you push you to the top. The positive emotions at work place can achieve wonder if exhibited whole heartedly. It helps an individual in following manners.

A. Ensures Intellectual Wellness.

Yes, surely a hurdle free mind is full of creativity and contributes to effective working of the organization. in todays competitive world creativity and innovations go hand in hand. Thus, with the help of positivity an individual can add up to the creativity and innovative process of the organization.

B. Improves health and well-being

Being positive or having positive emotions at workplace releases **Oxytocin**, a hormone produced by the hypothalamus and released by the pituitary gland that produces feelings of love and connection. Afterall it is all about getting connected.

C. Adapt to a better Lifestyle

A stress-free mind, less or no anxiety, are key sources for individual effectiveness. With positive emotions one can keep stress, anxiety, anger at bay by sorting to meditation, yoga, breathing techniques ect.

D. Ensures higher productivity and greater job satisfaction.

An organization does exist because of individuals and individuals do exist because of organization. A calm mind, rather a positive mind helps not only for higher productivity but also leaves an individual with greater job satisfaction. Again, job satisfaction is a soothing feeling which is a contributing factor for positivity.

E. Resilience

Yet another outcome of positive emotions at workplace is the Resilience, which means that an individual has a capacity to overcome through tough times, difficulties. Tough times and difficulties are the part and parcel of the organization. We cannot escape this situation even if we do not like it.

Positive emotions at work such as high achievement and excitement have “desirable effect irrespective of a person's relationships with others, including greater task activity, persistence and enhanced cognitive.” (Staw, Sutton, Pelled, 1994) “Strong positive emotions of intelligent people are embraced with optimism, positive or good mood, self-worth, and emotional flexibility to persist under opposing circumstances.” (Abraham, 1999).

“Optimism rests on the premise that failure is not inherent in the individual; it may be attributed to circumstances that may be changed with a refocusing of effort.” (Abraham, 1999) Those who express positive emotions in the workplace are better equipped to influence their coworkers favorably.

Now let us have a look at some **Negative** emotions. Problems which exist at domestic level, money related matters, disputes and misunderstandings with coworkers and a variety of other factors can cause your employees to come to work feeling nervous or miserable. Negative emotions can have a troublesome influence on the workplace because the individuals who are experiencing these feelings are often unable to focus on work. Furthermore, negative emotions are transmittable because unhappy workers often take out their frustrations on coworkers and even their supervisors. You cannot eliminate emotions from the workplace, but you can take steps to manage negative emotions. However, make sure you do not confuse managing emotions with suppressing emotions. Negativity is a powerful force and can spread quickly throughout an organization, especially if it is the predominant emotion witnessed in leaders. Many leaders will defend this perspective as they believe it is a

powerful motivator, and it may very well be for some employees and for some period of time.

But in the long run and for the majority of people, a negative perspective will suck the energy and productivity from an organization. It will reduce employee engagement and it will harm the bottom line.

Types of negative emotions

- Anger
- Disgust
- Fear
- Loneliness
- Self abuse
- Guilt
- Uncomfortable

Most common negative emotions at workplace and its impact on individuals

a) Anger

This is a most common negative emotion which all of us have. We find no person on the earth who exists without anger. We become angry for valid reasons, we become angry for silly reasons too. We feel as if anger is our birth right. Anger at workplace may be because of many reasons such as frustration, interpersonal conflicts, ego, envy to name a few. Anger produces adrenaline and cortisol, the hormone responsible for increasing stress and anxiety. Anger at work can lead to irrational behavior, such as explosive outbursts, or threatening to, or actually quitting one's job.

b) Envy.

This is the emotion although very common, is often suppressed at workplace. One does not show his envy towards his colleague openly. The reason for envy may be success of the co-worker, higher efficiency, junior-senior differentiation, favoritism etc.

c) Frustration

Frustration usually occurs when you feel stuck or trapped, or unable to move forward in some way. It may be because you may not get your desired project, or may be because of constant failures, or because of your own reluctance to do a work. This has a very negative impact on work performance.

Fig. 2: Types of Positive and Negative emotions and its effects

Impact of positive and negative emotions at work place

Positive emotions

- Enhances productivity
- Increased profitability
- High morale
- Motivation
- Conducive environment

Negative emotions

- Lower productivity
- Low morale
- Lack of motivation
- Absence of healthy environment
- Health problems

d) Findings and suggestions

- It is observed that positive emotion have a positive impact on the organization.
- Positive emotions not only keep the morale of the employees high but also act as a greatest motivating factor for productivity enhancement.
- Positive emotions are health boosters.
- Negative emotions on the other hand negative emotions are health busters.
- Negative emotions create an imbalance thus spoiling the organizational climate.

III. SUGGESTIONS

Effective management skills include more than getting the job done and meeting company targets. Being delicate to the non-work related concerns of employees can prove to be equally as important. Maintaining a non-aggressive work environment that balances the behaviors and needs of employees can effectively improve productivity and promote an healthy environment. Be practical, and take steps to avoid unnecessary emotional outbursts. Watch your anger and avoid uncontrolled conflicts which will bring out inappropriate emotions and behaviors.

Keep emotionally connected to your co workers. Ask questions to gauge how they are feeling in meetings and become attuned and sensitive to what makes them frustrated, sad, or angry. Encourage employees to act compassionately and in a caring way with one another throughout the workplace.

IV. CONCLUSION

Effective management skills include more than getting the job done through the employees and achieving the organizational and individual objectives. In this process, emotions play a vital role as we carry these wherever we go. Positive emotions have a positive impact on productivity while negative emotions adversely affect the work place environment. Thus we should manage the emotions in such a way that it not only leads to organizational effectiveness but also results in increased individual productivity.

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